

ATTITUDE TYPE AND ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS OF UNDERGRADUATES IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

OGUNWOYE, A. A.

College of Management and Social Sciences, Bowen University, Iwo, Nigeria.
Email: ogunwoye.adewuni@bowen.edu.ng wuniab2000@yahoo.com

OJOKUKU, R. M.

Faculty of Management Sciences, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho, Nigeria.
Email: rmojokuku@lautech.edu.ng

LAOSEBIKAN, J. O.

College of Management and Social Sciences, Bowen University, Iwo, Nigeria.
Email: johnson.olaosebikan@bowen.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, changing the mindset of university graduates from employee-oriented to entrepreneurial mindset is a major step being taken by both government and tertiary institutions for the purpose of curbing unemployment and promoting economic development. Achieving this objective has however been found to be a function of attitude type being formulated and held by the university students while still in university. This study examined the effect of attitude type on entrepreneurial intentions of undergraduates in public and private universities in Ogun state, Nigeria. A survey of one hundred and ninety nine final year students were randomly selected from three universities their responses were analysed using Multiple Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that 84% variation in entrepreneurship intentions is explained by both affective and instrumental attitude ($F_{1, 196} = 538.44$; $R^2 = 0.846$; $P < 0.000$) where affective attitude ($t = 5.50$; $P < 0.05$) was highly significant. The study concluded that university undergraduates will have high entrepreneurial intention when given chance to undergo course of their interest. It was recommended that parents be admonished to desist from compelling their wards to study courses that are not of their choice.

Key words: Entrepreneurial Intentions, Affective Attitude, Instrumental Attitude, Controlled Events, Informational Events

INTRODUCTION

The discrepancy between the rich and the poor, accumulative migration, and aging population are the major challenges confronted by globalization (Victoria, 2019). Government are searching for a solution that can produce a positive impact on socio-economic development one of the proposed solutions relate to the promotion of entrepreneurship (Victoria, 2019). The indigenously-owned-small and medium sized enterprises are perceived as the bedrock for sustainable economic development in the face of declining economy (Anthony and Florence, 2010). The informal sector account for approximately 50% of national output, over 80% of employment, and 90% of new jobs (Ahmadou, 2015). Therefore, it is believed that Nigerian Entrepreneurship is central to Nigeria's future prosperity (McNamee et al., 2015). As a result,

Rodeta and Evy (2015) predicted that changing the mindset of the well-educated unemployed from job-seeker into entrepreneur mindset is of utmost importance.

According to Iliya 2020, skills acquisition for entrepreneurship and job creation are critical for an economy that will require a boost post-covid-19. Osinbajo, (2020) observed that the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) slides to between minus 4.40 per cent and minus 8.91% during Covid-19 pandemic. According to Osinbajo, (2020) 39.4 million people might be unemployed by the end of 2020, if the government failed to take preemptive measures. It is therefore pertinent to note that the ongoing crisis of Covid 19 has a great effect on attitude which in turns influence the entrepreneurial intentions of the youth. It was noted according to Emine et. al., (2019) entrepreneurship intention is very significant in entrepreneurship activities. It was also noted that entrepreneurial attitude has a very significant role in predicting entrepreneurship attitude (Emine et. al., 2019).

STATEMENT PROBLEM AND OBJECTIVES

In recent years, academic institutions, especially the Nigerian private and public Universities, have been called upon to contribute to the development of entrepreneurship programmes through formal education and training. This is in recognition that skills acquisition for entrepreneurship and job creation are critical for an economy that will require a boost post-covid-19 (Iliya, 2020).

Richard (2005), revealed that despite several various programmes and schemes by Nigerian government, to make entrepreneurship thrive in Nigeria, which brought about the teaching of entrepreneurship education in colleges and universities in year 2004, studies have shown that the development of Entrepreneurship in Nigeria is still very slow (Diyoke, 2014). According to Bambale & Shika, 2016 this has resulted into high rate of unemployment mostly among the youths especially the university graduates. Ojeifo, (2013) also attributed the effect of unemployment among university graduates to dejection and high level of dependence on family, frustration and above all, a negative effect on economic growth and development of the nation.

Adelowo, Egbetokun & James (2015) discovered that personal interest is the most important motivator for undergraduate's entrepreneurship intention. It was however observed that there are different events that contribute to the formulation of different attitude which translates into different types of intentions.

As aptly observed earlier studies on entrepreneurship intentions (Oguntimehin & Olaniyan 2017; Surajo, Adewale & Ramoni 2016) focused mainly on the variables in the theory of planned behavior which only explain the extrinsic motivation, but neglect the aspect of the intrinsic motivation which has a psychological effect on intentions. The variable attitude was only explained as an external factor but did not explain the existence of different type of events which explains the type of attitude that may arise from these events which in turn affects the degree of entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, these different types of attitudes needs to be

investigated in order to know which affects the intentions of undergraduates in the public and private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. Hence, the reason for this study.

HYPOTHESES

H₀: Affective attitude does not have a significant impact on entrepreneurship intentions among public and private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria

H₀: Instrumental attitude does not have a significant impact on entrepreneurship intentions among public and private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria

RELATED STUDIES

ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS

Entrepreneurial intention has been receiving a wide and great attention from scholars especially before the covid 19 crisis, ranging from researchers both outside Nigeria and in Nigeria. According to Krueger, Reilly, and Carsrud (2000), The Theory of Planned Behaviour proved that intention is the best predictor of planned behavior. In actual fact, the Theory of Planned Behaviour revealed that entrepreneurship is a planned behavior. (Krueger et al., 2000). The decision to become an entrepreneur is not an overnight decision but a deliberate and mindful process (Liñán & Chen, 2011). As opined by Aviram (2010), looking at some businesses, it will be observed that they are created after going through a mindful process, not by accident or suddenly. It is however to be noted that entrepreneurial intentions is vital to understanding entrepreneurship itself. Thompson, 2009 opined that entrepreneurial intention is a very important and critical element in entrepreneurship theory and construct. According to Schlaegel and Koenig (2013) it is the central point to understanding entrepreneurship and also the original step in the entrepreneurship process of discovering, creating, and exploiting opportunities.

THE SELF DETERMINATION THEORY (SDT)

According to Alex, (2011), Self Determination Theory has been argued to be a motivational paradigm which explains human behavior in terms of psychological needs fulfillment. These three needs are known as autonomy, competence and relatedness.

Autonomy: This is defined as the freedom of choice. Autonomy is high when individuals feel they are engaging in a particular task because they chose to do so, not because they feel pressured by others or external factors. So, they can self-determine what to do.

Competence: This is defined by a perceived self-belief in one's ability to perform well in an activity. People need to feel challenged, contributing to the cause and being effective.

Relatedness: This is defined by a sense of shared experience. People need to care and be cared for.

THE THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOUR (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behaviour is one of the most widely tested theories of behavior in the history of the academy (Ajzen, 2011). It posits that engagement in future behavior is governed by one's intention. Intention reflects the behavioural orientation and commitment towards a future action, and is proposed to be predicted by three belief-based social-cognitive variables; attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavior control as antecedents of intention (Ajzen, 2011). Perceived behavioral control is an antecedent of behaviour as well as an antecedent of intention. Attitude encompasses an individual's evaluation of the benefits of engaging in particular behavior. Subjective norms are the opinions of an individual's significant others relative to the behavior under consideration. Perceived behavior control addresses an individual's perception of being able to accomplish the contemplated behavior. According to Jonathan, (2017) a casual reading of TPB reveals a primarily extrinsic focus. The construct of attitude is extrinsic in terms of how it was formulated as an instrumental focus. Subjective norms, the opinions of significant others, are purely extrinsic. Even perceived behavioral control has an extrinsic mode it relates to how an individual is able to operate within the extended world.

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN SDT AND TPB

Ajzen, (2011) has conceded that the focus of the theory is goal-oriented behavior. For behaviours that are not goal oriented, the theory may not offer as much explanation. Self Determination Theory (SDT) is a theory of motivation that aims to explain individual's goal-directed behavior (Alex, 2011). SDT is built on the assumption that humans are intrinsically motivated toward learning, growth and intellectual challenge (Geofery, Ronald, Lisa and Edward, 1997). SDT, while exploring the foundation of intrinsic motivation, is an approach to personality that focuses on an individual's psychological needs and how those needs interact with self-motivation (Ryan and Deci 2000). However, different events occur that tend to affect the outcome of the different elements in the two theories that is the Informational event and the Controlled event.

INFORMATIONAL EVENT

This is an event whereby an individual feels free to engage in a particular act. This act makes him/her to be self-fulfilled in high degree and happy. The act is being done out of that individual's accord. The individual here enjoys what he or she is doing.

CONTROLLED EVENT

This is an event whereby the individual finds himself engaging in an activity but is not happy or does not enjoy doing it. Such individual only does it to fulfill an obligation towards the external forces, such as family desire. Such individual also feels the sense of self-fulfillment but not in high degree.

EFFECT OF INFORMATIONAL AND CONTROLLED EVENT ON SDT

The Self Determination Theory is concerned with the motivation of humans to achieve autonomy. Such autonomy occurs when individuals are free to engage in self-determined behavior. One of the factors that affect perception of autonomy in decision making is described as the constructs of informational and controlling events (Jonathan, 2016).

Informational events: This is an event whereby an individual feels freely to engage in while feeling the sense of self-fulfillment. The individual here enjoys what he or she is doing and freely achieve autonomy as his/her self-fulfillment increases.

Controlled events: This is an event whereby the individual finds himself doing it but is not happy or does not enjoy doing it. Such individual only does it to fulfill an obligation towards the external forces, such as family desire. Such individual also feels the sense of self-fulfillment but not in high degree.

EFFECT OF INFORMATIONAL AND CONTROLLED EVENT ON TPB

The perception of the factors that affect autonomy i.e controlled event and informational event, in the self-determination theory also tend to affect the three variables in the theory of planned behavior. The elements of controlled and information events within the decomposed model of Hagger, et al (2005) addresses attitude in two ways. The Instrumental attitude and the Affective attitude. The instrumental attitude is a function of an individual believes that positive outcome will result due to some behavior, then that individual is more likely to develop intention to engage in that behavior. This can be liken to occur within the controlled event. The Affective attitude elates to how the individual expects to enjoy engaging in a specific behavior. The more enjoyment the individual expects, the more likely they are to engage in the behaviour. This is liken to occur within the context of the informational events.

The subjective norms are derived by Hagger, et al (2005) that this is divided into two namely the injunctive norm and the descriptive norms. Injunctive norms are those behaviours of which individuals perceived their significant others will approve for example if an individual feels that if he starts a particular skill training his friends, family and other important people to him/her will like it, this will develop the intention of engaging in the skill training. Descriptive norms on the other hand are those behaviours in which individuals' friends actually engage in that skill training and this will develop intention to join them in the training, it's not that the individual really likes it or enjoys it, but because of group or family influence.

Perceived Behavioural Control is also said to have two elements according to Hagger et al (1985). Those elements are self-efficacy and perceived control. Self-efficacy relates to how skilled individuals perceived themselves to be relative to some activity. If individual use to sing in school choir, they may perceive themselves that skill with respect to singing and may develop their intention to train to be singers even after graduation. Perceived control relates to the access individuals have for some activity, if an individual who sings very well while in school gets involve in an accident which claims her voice, such may be less likely to develop

intention to be a singer after graduation. This explanations above is depicted in the model below termed by Hagger et al (2005) as decomposed TPB

TYPES OF ATTITUDE DERIVED FROM DIFFERENT EVENTS

From the diagram above, it will be seen that different attitude as well as other elements occur depending on the type of event an individual finds himself. The type of attitude that occurs here are the Affective and Instrumental attitude.

Affective Attitude: This occur when an individual finds himself under the informational event. This type of attitude tend to help the individual in developing a positive intention that is growth oriented. Individual who develops this type of attitude tend to have high degree of intention, and such individual creative mind will be high such that even when passing through obstacles, they will strive to achieve their aim in order to be self fulfilled. Individual possessed by this type of attitude always strive to sustain their entrepreneurial activities not only starting it, but also sustaining it to a developed stage.

Instrumental Attitude: This occur when an individual finds himself under the controlled event. This type of attitude does not bring about high degree of self-fulfillment. This is because, the individual is engaging in an activity in order to satisfy a third party and not himself. When such an individual finds any slightest chance of freeing himself out of that activity, he will not hesitate to disengage from such activities, this is because it goal directed. Such and individual may not see to the sustainability of such act and may be easily affected by any slight challenge, and such individual's creative mind will not be high.

METHODOLOGY

The target population for this study were final year students in the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences from three universities (public and private universities) in Ogun State. A sample of 200 was selected through simple random sampling and a structured questionnaire was used to gather relevant data by the means of Google form. Multiple Regression Analysis was used in the analysis which comprises various tests such as F-test, r^2 and the adjusted r^2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The result revealed that 123 (61.81%) are female while 76 (38.19%) are male. Furthermore, 199 (100%) of the respondents are single and are all final year undergraduates in the faculty of Social and Management Sciences.

The Multiple Regression Analysis table showed that both Affective and Instrumental Attitude has a significant effect ($F_{1, 196} = 538.44$; $R^2 = 0.846$; $P < 0.0000$) on Entrepreneurship Intentions. Table 1 reveals the predictive effect of affective attitude and instrumental attitude on entrepreneurship intentions. The table equally shows that the value R^2 0.846 is significantly tending to unity (1) which suggests that the model is well fitted. By implication, the predictor variables explained 84% of the variations in entrepreneurship intentions. Furthermore, the

result revealed that affective attitude ($t = 5.50$; $P < 0.05$) was highly significant. Also, the instrumental attitude ($t = 4.76$; $P < 0.05$) was highly significant

The Multiple Regression Analysis was also used to test the formulated hypothesis as seen in table 1 below and based on this result, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted.

Table1: Multiple Regression Analysis Showing Effect of Attitude Type on Entrepreneurial Intentions

Model	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Root MSE		
1	0.8460	0.8444	0.73689		
Source	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Model	584.755931	2	292.377966	538.44	0.0000
Residual	106.429999	196	0.5430010197		
Total	691.18593	198	3.49083803		
Model	Coef	Std. Error	T	Sig	
(Constant)	0.3736724	0.1188452	3.14	0.002	
Informative	0.2521601	0.0458083	5.50	0.000	
Instrumental	0.2177041	0.0457509	4.76	0.000	

Source: Field survey, 2021

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The objective of this study was to investigate the type of attitude that most effect the entrepreneurship intentions of undergraduates in public and private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. Both affective attitude and instrumental attitude effect were measured by undergraduate's opinion on the course of their studies on entrepreneurship intentions. Findings revealed that affective attitude has the highest significant effect on entrepreneurship intentions. Findings also revealed that most of the respondents were on their course of study based on their interest and choice, it was however noticed from the result that, there is no significant difference between those who study the course of their choice and those who study the course mandated for them to study either by parents or circumstances. This could be due to what the school offered them to study or lack of qualified requirements to study the course of their choice.

It can be concluded from the findings that affective attitude needs to be given more attention by allowing youths to study their course of choice. This will go a long way to trigger the intrinsic motivation of the youth on entrepreneurship because this will be done with passion and commitment. The outcome of this will be high sustainability and growth of entrepreneurship which will have a direct positive impact on economic growth. During this post-CODID-19 era, the most important

Based on these findings, it is recommended that:

* Youths should be allowed to study the course of their interest as this will be done with enthusiasm and passion

* Universities should make provisions whereby even if the potential student does not have recommended qualification to study course of interest at first, they can be given the chance by organizing an internal examination to make them qualified.

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